

Deliverable 3.1

S-LCA of two selected hydrogen systems and set of indicators for citizenship

The project is supported by the Clean Hydrogen Partnership and its members.

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D 3.1	S-LCA of two selected hydrogen systems and set of indicators for citizenship
DELIVERABLE TYPE	Report
MONTH AND DATE OF DELIVERABLE	Month 25, 30/06/2025
WORK PACKAGE	WP 3
LEADER	IME
DISSEMINATION LEVEL	Public
AUTHORS	S.K.R. Maddula, J. Dufour, D. Iribarren
PROGRAMME	HORIZON EUROPE
GRANT AGREEMENT	101111933
START	Jun. 2023
DURATION	28 Months

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Revision History

VERSION	DATE	ORGANISATION	MODIFICATIONS
1	28/05/2025	IME	Complete version for internal review
2	27/06/2025	IME	Final version after internal review

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Acronyms

FCB	Fuel Cell Bus
HRS	Hydrogen Refuelling Station
IRENA	International Renewable Energy Agency
PEM	Proton Exchange Membrane
PSILCA	Product Social Impact Life Cycle Assessment
PV	Photovoltaic
S-LCA	Social Life Cycle Assessment
S-LCI	Social Life Cycle Inventory
S-LCIA	Social Life Cycle Impact Assessment

Executive Summary

Deliverable 3.1 details the work carried out in Task 3.1 under work package 3 (citizens' engagement) of the HYPOP project. In this task, a social life cycle assessment was performed for two case studies: one focusing on hydrogen production and the other on urban mobility. The methodological approach was based on the work conducted in Task 4.1 regarding an assessment framework for reporting to citizens. This document highlights the importance of progress in social assessment and its role in enhancing sustainability outcomes for emerging technologies like hydrogen-related ones.

1 Introduction

The world is moving towards decarbonisation, seeking sustainable solutions to achieve a low-carbon economy. The energy sector is one of the largest contributors to global emissions. This has driven research into emerging energy technologies that either eliminate carbon emissions or significantly reduce them through safe and sustainable strategies. These emerging technologies are expected to transform current energy systems, ensuring their sustainability for future generations.

In particular, hydrogen is expected to play an important role in mitigating carbon emissions (IRENA, 2024). It is abundantly available indirectly, e.g. in water and hydrocarbons. Around 2% of global hydrogen is sourced from water electrolysis, which highlights the need to further promote clean hydrogen production technologies. Moreover, it is crucial to utilise hydrogen efficiently. While many industries consider the use of hydrogen to replace carbon-intensive energy sources, there remains a significant need for its adoption in the transport sector.

When assessing the sustainability of hydrogen-based solutions, social aspects should be thoroughly addressed. However, most sustainability assessments for cases such as hydrogen production in refuelling stations and hydrogen use in fuel cell buses (FCBs) are focused on environmental and economic aspects while leaving social assessments largely untouched (Cockroft and Owen, 2006; Wulf and Kaltschmitt, 2012; Lubecki et al., 2023; Wu et al., 2024).

In this context, this deliverable of the HYPOP project addresses existing gaps by conducting social life cycle assessment (S-LCA) studies for two cases: hydrogen production through electrolysis powered by renewable onsite electricity at a hydrogen refuelling station (HRS), and urban mobility based on hydrogen use in FCBs. Thus, this report illustrates the role of social assessment to actively engage citizens in the transition to hydrogen-related technologies such as electrolyzers and fuel cells.

2 Methodological specifications & case studies

The specific S-LCA methodology followed in this report corresponds to the S-LCA framework for reporting to citizens developed in HYPOP Deliverable 4.1 (Maddula et al., 2024). This involves four stages as described below.

The first stage of the assessment is **goal and scope**. The goal of this study is to illustrate how S-LCA works through two hydrogen-relevant cases. The purpose is to identify social hotspots (i.e. areas of potential social risk or impact) that are relevant to citizens. Different functional units (i.e. quantified description of the system's function) were considered for each case study, depending on their goal and scope, as defined in their respective sections (2.1 and 2.2). The system boundaries of the two cases refer to: renewable hydrogen production at an HRS (case 1) and how that hydrogen is used to power bus transport service in FCBs (case 2) as shown in Figure 1. Both cases, depicted in Figure 1 with their involved supporting components, cover manufacturing and operation life cycle stages of the systems being analysed.

Stakeholder categories represent groups of people or organisations (e.g. workers, local communities, consumers, or regulators) that are affected (positively or negatively) by activities carried out by industries and organisations in the product's life cycle. S-LCA guidelines recommend different approaches (Benoît Norris et al., 2020) to identify which stakeholders are relevant for a particular product or process. In this study, the researchers used lessons learnt from a previous European project

eGHOST (which focused on sustainable-by-design hydrogen technologies) to decide which stakeholder groups were relevant for their assessment (Iribarren et al., 2021). The identified stakeholders are presented later in Table 1.

Figure 1 System boundaries of the two case studies

Social life cycle inventory (S-LCI) is the second stage of the S-LCA methodology. This stage involves collecting the inventory data based on how much labour (measured in worker hours) was used (activity variable) per functional unit. When worker hours were not directly available, they were estimated indirectly using the economic values with respect to the identified country and sector (i.e. how many worker hours were typically involved in producing a certain monetary value of goods in a given sector). Inventory data was compiled based on the design of the product system to reach the functional unit. To determine which countries the components originated from, the protocol developed by Martín-Gamboa et al. (2020) was used. The compiled inventory data and the identified countries of origin information are presented later in Section 3.

Social life cycle impact assessment (S-LCIA) is the third stage, evaluating the social impacts of the activities identified in the first stage (goal and scope) according to the inventory built in the previous stage (S-LCI). The evaluation procedure detailed in Deliverable 4.1 (Maddula et al., 2024) was followed, ensuring consistency with an established and peer-reviewed framework. The developed inventory data were computationally implemented in the PSILCA database in openLCA software to link inventory data to social risk indicators. It transforms raw data (e.g. worker hours) into meaningful social impact results (expressed in medium risk hours –mrh– or medium opportunity hours –moh–) by multiplying it with risk factors corresponding to each social indicator. Similarly, if the input data is provided in economic values, the background process in PSILCA undergoes an additional step where

economic values are transformed into worker hours; subsequently, the same procedure is followed to evaluate social impacts. The assessed social indicators for both cases are presented in Table 1 (Loubert et al., 2023).

The final stage of the assessment is the **interpretation** of the results, clarifying what the findings actually imply. Social hotspots identification was performed across the supply chains defined for both cases to clarify specific countries, sectors, or processes with elevated risk of negative social impacts (e.g. poor working conditions, human rights concerns) and opportunities for economic growth. Furthermore, the identified hotspots were visually represented in the form of a dashboard as an important add-on feature of the framework for reporting to citizens, making the results easier to understand and more engaging.

Table 1 Selected stakeholder categories and social indicators

Sustainable development goals	Stakeholder categories	Social indicators	Definition	Factors
Decent work and economic growth; No poverty	Workers	Fair salary	Wage offered to a particular service corresponding to its respective value	Minimum wage required by law; Local prevailing industrial wage; Living wage
Gender equality		Gender wage gap	Difference between median earning of men and women relative to median earning of men	Median earning by gender
Decent work and economic growth		Forced labour	Work or service that people are compelled to perform without their consent, under the menace of a negative consequence, and often without receiving fair wages	Relationship between person performing and exacting the work; Human trafficking; Debt bondage; Exploitation of children
		Child labour	Children aged 7-14 involved in economic activity for at least one hour in the reference week	Children involved
Good health and well being	Society	Contribution to economic development	Extent to which a sector contributes to the economic development of a country	Sector contribution to GDP; Public education expenditure; Literacy rate
		Health expenditure	Indicator assessing health systems of the countries	Health status of society; Public health expenditure; Public health coverage; etc.

Each of the two case studies has its unique goal and scope, involving different functional units and different levels (tiers) of components along with their technical definition, as detailed in the following sub-sections.

2.1 Renewable hydrogen production at an HRS (case 1)

The goal of the proposed HRS is to provide hydrogen produced onsite using a 54.5 kWh/kg H₂ proton exchange membrane (PEM) electrolyser (Yates et al., 2020), a device that splits water into hydrogen and oxygen using electricity. To power the electrolyser, photovoltaic (PV) electricity from a 6 MW onsite solar installation with monocrystalline half-cut panels was considered (Smith et al., 2021), along with grid electricity support. The functional unit for this case is the production of 1 kg of hydrogen at the HRS in Spain, which allows impacts to be measured in a consistent way. The system boundary of the HRS includes various components, as shown in Figure 1 for case 1. Additionally, Figure 2 illustrates the extended components and their respective countries of origin. In addition to the PEM electrolyser, the system also includes a compressor, a hydrogen storage tank (James et al., 2016a) and PV panels, along with other supporting components such as the battery inverter, controller, etc. that were considered. The origin countries of all these involved components were identified following the protocol developed by Martín-Gamboa et al. (2020), which helps assess country-specific social risks.

Figure 2 Hydrogen refuelling station components and country of origin

The HRS was designed to operate, overall, for 24 hours a day. The onsite solar (PV) panel installation was designed with consideration of space availability; specifically, the surface constraints based on the area occupied by Madrid South Bus Station. The design had to balance energy needs with land use constraints. Data for different PV capacities were assessed from PVGIS (2024), a tool for estimating solar energy output, by selecting four representative months (one month from each season), to subsequently estimate annual energy production. This process was repeated for various PV capacities, with the 6 MW PV capacity being identified as the optimal solution with respect to the surface area

occupied and on-site electricity share. PV generation accounted for 54.46% of the electricity needs for the HRS annually. The size of the PEM electrolyser was chosen to accommodate the refuelling of over 100 buses per day. Other technical parameters (e.g. storage capacity, compression levels) for the HRS were based on compatible literature (Elgowainy et al., 2017; Poudel et al., 2024), as presented in Table 2.

Table 2 Technical parameters of the HRS

Item	Value	Units
PEM electrolyser: power	6.5	MW
PEM electrolyser: number of stacks	13	stacks
PEM electrolyser: operating pressure	1-30	bar
Compressor	200 to 450	bar
Type IV storage tank	350	bar
Pre-cooling unit	-20 to -30	°C
Dispenser	3.1	kg/min

2.2 Bus transport service for urban mobility (case 2)

In this study, bus transport service in Spain includes both hydrogen use in FCBs and hydrogen supply at the HRS as a combined system. The functional unit was defined as 15 passenger-kilometres, meaning that the social impacts were calculated based on transporting passengers a combined total of 15 km (e.g. 15 passengers for 1 km each, or 1 passenger for 15 km). The system boundary of the study includes all the components and stages shown in Figure 1. Moreover, the components involved in the bus transport service are depicted in Figure 2 for the HRS and Figure 3 for the FCB.

Figure 3 Fuel cell bus components with their respective identified country of origin

Regarding the technical definition for the bus transport service, hydrogen at the HRS was considered to be produced for 11 hours during the day through PEM electrolysis. The produced hydrogen is compressed and stored in a Type IV storage vessel (lightweight, high-pressure tank) at the HRS, which provides a storage capacity for 3 days and 12 hours (usage-based design). The stored hydrogen at the HRS is pre-cooled and dispensed to the FCBs during the night with three dispensers when buses are not in service. Hydrogen is filled in the fuel tank up to 11 kg in 3.548 minutes, indicating a fast-refuelling process. Technical parameters of the FCB, based on compatible literature (James et al., 2016b; Neis, 2019), are presented in Table 3.

Table 3 Technical parameters of the fuel cell bus

Item	Value	Units
PEM fuel cell: power	160	kW
PEM fuel cell: number of stacks	2	stacks
Chassis	11	m
Passenger capacity	44	passengers
Type III, storage tank	350	bar
Bus economy	11	km/kg H ₂
Passenger occupancy rate	50	%

3 Results

The results for each case study include inventory data (Sections 3.1.1 and 3.2.1) and social risks (Sections 3.1.2 and 3.2.2).

3.1 Results for HRS (case 1)

Inventory data for the items involved in the HRS were quantified per functional unit and implemented in openLCA over the PSILCA database for the evaluation of the social risk profile.

3.1.1 Inventory data results for HRS

Inventory data for the HRS case study are presented in Table 4, either directly as worker hours (labour input) or indirectly as economic values (used to estimate worker hours when direct data were unavailable). All the inventory data provided in the table were adjusted to 1 kg of hydrogen at the HRS (functional unit) to allow for consistent implementation. Although the data extracted from the literature originate from various sources, the economic data presented in Table 4 were aligned to the same reference year to maintain consistency in the assessment.

Table 4 Inventory data per kg H₂ at HRS (h: worker hours; p: pieces)

Parent system (Country)	Item (Country)	Amount per kg H ₂
HRS (ES)	Hydrogen product (ES)	1.09E-01 h
	Pre-cooling system (SE)	2.16E-02 \$
	Dispenser (UK)	1.51E-02 \$
	Compressor (US)	9.58E-08 p; 1.07E-04 h
	H ₂ storage tank (DE)	9.58E-08 p; 4.84E-04 h
	PEM electrolyser (US)	9.58E-08 p; 5.86E-05 h
	PV panels (CN)	1.34E-03 p; 2.38E-07 h
	PV mounting system (ES)	2.52E-01 \$
	Transformer (CN)	1.21E-02 \$
	Battery inverter (CN)	5.19E-02 \$
	Controller (DE)	4.36E-02 \$
	Electricity (ES)	1.87E-01 \$
Compressor (US)	Diaphragms (CN)	4.79E-03 \$
	Compressor parts (CN)	2.49E-02 \$
	Plates and cavities (CN)	8.62E-03 \$
	Electric motor (MX)	9.58E-03 \$
	Electricity (US)	2.66E-05 \$
H ₂ storage tank (DE)	T700 carbon fibre (DE)	9.08E-01 \$
	Electricity (DE)	1.44E-03 \$
PEM electrolyser (US)	Catalyst coated membrane (US)	3.42E-02 \$
	Porous transport layer (JP)	1.68E-02 \$
	Seal/frame (TW)	1.87E-03 \$
	Bipolar plates (TW)	8.72E-03 \$
	AC/DC rectifier (CN)	1.24E-01 \$
	O ₂ separator tank (MX)	2.49E-02 \$
	Pumps (CN)	9.94E-03 \$
	Piping (KR)	1.56E-02 \$
	Valves (CN)	1.84E-02 \$
	Controller (MX)	6.44E-03 \$
	Dryer (CN)	2.28E-02 \$
	Hydrogen separator (MX)	1.64E-02 \$
	Plate heat exchanger (MX)	1.12E-02 \$
	Electricity (US)	5.23E-06 \$
Natural gas (US)	1.59E-04 \$	
PV panels (CN)	Aluminium backsheet (CN)	3.20E-05 \$
	Front glass (65% CN, 23% JP, 12% TW)	1.51E-04 \$
	EVA film (59% KR, 41% TW)	1.46E-05 \$
	Electricity (CN)	1.72E-06 \$

3.1.2 Social risks for HRS

Following the recommendations in Iribarren et al. (2021) and Maddula et al. (2024), the six social indicators considered by default for evaluation in S-LCA were used: forced labour, gender wage gap, child labour, fair salary, health expenditure, and contribution to economic growth. Figure 4 depicts the evaluated social risks per functional unit (i.e. per 1 kg of hydrogen produced at the HRS). The main social hotspot identified under each social indicator is visually indicated with a red (adverse risk) or green (positive opportunity) arrow in the dashboard. The label “Hydrogen” in Figure 4 represents the labour (worker hours) at the HRS in Spain required to provide the functional unit (1 kg H₂ produced at the HRS), which was identified as the social hotspot for forced labour and gender wage gap (two of the six social indicators). For the remaining four indicators (child labour, fair salary, health expenditure, and economic growth), the battery inverter sourced from China was identified as the main social hotspot. However, it should be noted that one of the remaining four indicators (economic growth) involves an opportunity, not an adverse risk.

Figure 4 Social risks associated with the HRS case study (mrh: medium risk hours; moh: medium opportunity hours)

Overall, S-LCA application successfully led to a thorough assessment of the HRS case study across various social aspects, including the identification of risks (e.g. labour issues) and opportunities (e.g. economic growth) for different stakeholder groups. Comparison of the results with other S-LCA studies such as that on hydrogen production in Spain by Valente et al. (2021) was considered inappropriate due to important differences in the scale (e.g. size or production volume) and scope (e.g. which parts of the life cycle are included) of hydrogen production, as well as different PSILCA database versions used (which affects how risks are measured and interpreted). Finally, it should be highlighted that, to enrich and contextualise the S-LCA results reported in this study, it is recommended that several complementary procedures should be utilised, such as surveys (to gather perspectives from affected groups), workshops (to engage stakeholders directly), and media communications (to inform and involve the public). These methods help address the real-world concerns and perceptions of citizens, end users, and other stakeholders in society.

3.2 Results for bus transport service (case 2)

Inventory data for the items involved in the bus transport service system were quantified per functional unit and implemented in openLCA over the PSILCA database for the evaluation of the social risk profile.

3.2.1 Inventory data results for bus transport service

The compiled inventory results for the bus transport service system are provided in Table 5. In this table, “hydrogen at HRS” represents the amount of hydrogen required by the FCB to reach the functional unit (15 passenger-kilometres). The corresponding inventory data of hydrogen at HRS are those in Table 4 multiplied by 6.20E-02 kg H₂, as the amount of hydrogen required to meet the functional unit. “Hydrogen bus operation” represents the labour (driver hours) involved in operating the hydrogen bus for the functional unit. Although the data extracted from the literature originate from various sources, the economic data presented in Table 5 were aligned to the same reference year to maintain consistency in the assessment.

Table 5 Inventory data for bus transport service (h: worker hours; p: pieces)

Parent system (Country)	Item (Country)	Amount
Bus transport service (ES)	Hydrogen bus operation (ES)	0.07 h
	Hydrogen at HRS (ES)	6.20E-02 kg; Table 4
	FCB (ES)	3.98E-06 p; 7.76E-03 h
FCB (ES)	PEM fuel cell (CN)	3.98E-06 p; 6.26E-05 h
	Traction battery (CN)	7.04E-10 \$
	Electric motor (DE)	2.01E-02 \$
	H ₂ fuel tank (ES)	5.86E-02 \$
	Gearbox (ES)	8.38E-03 \$
	Chassis (SE)	3.98E-06 p; 1.73E-04 h
	Brake drum (FR)	3.30E-03 \$
	AC compressor (DE)	2.79E-03 \$
	Shock absorbers (ES)	2.37E-02 \$
	Tyres (ES)	3.98E-03 \$
	Drive axle (IT)	2.07E-03 \$
	Differential (IT)	1.20E-03 \$
	Inverter (DE)	1.87E-03 \$
	Electricity (ES)	1.46E-02 \$
Chassis (SE)	Steel (41.8% DE, 38.5% CN, 10.2% PL, 9.5% DK)	9.23E-02 \$
	Electricity (SE)	7.06E-03 \$
	Natural gas (RU)	5.66E-03 \$
PEM fuel cell (CN)	Membrane (CN)	3.15E-02 \$
	Catalyst ink (US)	4.36E-02 \$
	Gas diffusion layer (CN)	2.34E-02 \$
	Gaskets and bands (CN)	6.12E-03 \$
	Plates (CN)	1.60E-02 \$
	Current collectors (US)	9.50E-05 \$
	Stack housing (CN)	6.65E-04 \$
	Air compressor (CN)	2.45E-02 \$
	Humidifier (CN)	3.40E-03 \$
	Radiators (CN)	7.92E-03 \$
	Purge valves (CN)	3.53E-03 \$
	Current sensor (KR)	3.48E-03 \$
	Fittings (CN)	3.03E-03 \$
	System controller (TW)	1.05E-03 \$
Electricity (CN)	1.56E-03 \$	

3.2.2 Social risks for bus transport service

The social risks evaluated for the bus transport service system per functional unit are shown in Figure 5. For the child labour indicator, the FCB was found to involve the highest contribution. A breakdown of the FCB into components led to identify the chassis, the PEM fuel cell, and the hydrogen bus manufacturing plant as the major contributors.

The economic growth indicator shows that 53% of the medium opportunity hours would come from the FCB, while 40% would be linked to hydrogen at the HRS. The opportunities within the FCB were further broken down into components, with the main contribution attributed to the chassis, the PEM fuel cell, and the hydrogen bus manufacturing plant.

In the remaining four indicators (forced labour, fair salary, health expenditure, and gender wage gap), hydrogen bus operation was identified as the key social hotspot. For the forced labour indicator, this was found to be mainly due to the relatively high number of worker hours required for operation. On the other hand, for the gender wage gap indicator, the role of high risk levels was found critical in the sector and region where the bus driving occurs. For the health expenditure and fair salary indicators, a combined effect of risk levels and worker hours was found.

Figure 5 Social risks associated with bus transport service (mrh: medium risk hours; moh: medium opportunity hours)

Comparison of the results with other S-LCA studies on FCBs was not found feasible due to the lack of comparable studies in this field. On the other hand, for contextualisation purposes, the work conducted by Campos-Carriedo et al. (2024) on fuel cell electric cars was considered. The contextualisation of the results indicates that the social impacts of cars per passenger-kilometre could be higher than those of FCBs largely due to the efficient shared usage of buses by multiple passengers, as buses carry more people at once.

The S-LCA results for hydrogen production and use successfully enabled the identification of social hotspots in the bus transport service case study across various social aspects, including issues such as labour risks or economic opportunity. To enrich these S-LCA results, additional engagement methods

should be utilised, such as online polls, stakeholder consultations, workshops, and media communications. These methods can bring in public and stakeholder perspectives, making the social assessment more complete and tailored.

4 Conclusions

The S-LCA methodology was effectively applied to two illustrative hydrogen-related case studies in Spain, aligned with the framework for reporting to citizens developed in HYPOP Task 4.1. Inventory data were compiled to enable the analysis, and key social hotspots were identified and graphically visualised. The findings indicate that the main sources of social risk included the battery inverter plant, hydrogen at HRS, the PEM fuel cell, and the chassis, along with hydrogen bus operation. These were the components or processes most associated with negative social indicators (e.g. labour issues, wage gaps, health expenditure concerns). Across the countries, social hotspots were found to be concentrated in China (linked to its leading role in the supply chain of components), besides Spain as the host country. It should be noted that performing S-LCA studies is inherently case-specific. In particular, the results are significantly influenced by the reference country for which the analysis is conducted – in this case, Spain.

In the context of the HYPOP project, the outcomes of this S-LCA study serve multiple purposes. They illustrate a strategic framework for evaluating the social sustainability of hydrogen-related technologies, particularly for the worker and society stakeholder groups. For example, indicators such as fair salary and gender wage gap directly inform discussions around labour rights and equality, while forced and child labour indicators highlight potential human rights concerns within the involved supply chains. Furthermore, this study helps engage and inform public in HYPOP events with science-based insights. At broader level, it initiates narratives/discussion related to hydrogen within the society through fair transition lens. The S-LCA results also illustrate the potential to bridge the gap between public perception and policy or corporate strategy towards a socially responsible hydrogen economy. Finally, continuous alignment with progress in the field of S-LCA is recommended to further enhance the potential of this methodology when it comes to supplementing other social analysis procedures relevant to hydrogen-related systems.

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